

Solar Radiation Modification

Background

In November 2026, climate negotiators at the 31st Conference of the Parties summit (COP31) in Australia [1] agreed on a framework to deploy solar radiation modification (SRM), amidst substantial protests from civil society attendees in the summit's more informal "green zone." Protestors at subsequent climate events around the world have demanded greater commitment to mitigating greenhouse gas emissions, and public opinion is split. Many developing nations in South America and Africa are extremely concerned about potential impacts on agriculture and ecotourism due to shifting precipitation patterns [2], and others view SRM as a new form of climate injustice perpetrated by wealthy nations on the rest of the world.

It is now the year 2030, and test deployments of SRM using stratospheric aerosol injection (SAI) of sulfur dioxide (SO₂) are nonetheless proceeding. Plans are designed to confirm the costs, payload per sortie, operational pace, and other characteristics of high-altitude platforms for injection of a sulfate precursor into the atmosphere at 25 km altitude (approximately 82,000 ft). [3]

Incidents have occurred on two out of five recent test flights. In the first, a modified rocket-assisted subsonic version of the SAI Lofted aircraft (SAIL-01) was scheduled to deliver an aerosol payload of 18,000 pounds (8.2 metric tonnes), but an altimeter malfunction caused the deployment to begin at 17 km altitude. In the second, a modified supersonic cruiser based on the SR-71 Blackbird was loaded with what was later determined to be a different (and non-reactive) chemical than what was intended as the payload. The first flight originated in Australia, while the second was from the United States.

These incidents received major media coverage, and as of now, independent investigations have not determined the cause of either episode. No one has claimed responsibility, and investigators have not ruled out the possibility that both occurrences were accidental. Most view this as unlikely, however, given the scrutiny surrounding the tests and that a major issue occurred on more than one flight.

Roles

This scenario includes five different roles. Participants in these roles should propose a course of action that advocates for their assigned point of view. These courses of action should reflect information about required resources, knowledge gaps to close, incident response, etc.

- Diplomatic
 - Coordinating international communications
 - Examining and proposing legal ramifications
- Cybersecurity
 - Assessing extent of technical impacts in systems, evaluating insider threats
 - Proposing futureproof solutions to eliminate other attack surfaces

- Public Affairs
 - Coordinating public relations communications after the incidents and during the investigations
- National Security
 - Determining impacts to future planned tests
 - Investigating potential tampering with supply chain
- Climate
 - Examining consequences to climate if alternative plans for use of SRM emerge as a result of the incidents

References

1. Australian Government. 2022. “Australia’s Biennial Communication – December 2022.” https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/Australia_2nd_Biennial%20Climate%20Finance%20Communication%20to%20UNFCCC%20FINAL.pdf
2. O'Neill, B., M. van Aalst, Z. Zaiton Ibrahim, L. Berrang Ford, S. Bhadwal, H. Buhaug, D. Diaz, K. Frieler, M. Garschagen, A. Magnan, G. Midgley, A. Mirzabaev, A. Thomas, and R. Warren, 2022: Key Risks Across Sectors and Regions. In: Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lösschke, V. Möller, A. Okem, B. Rama (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, pp. 2411–2538, doi:10.1017/9781009325844.025.
3. Smith, W., Bhattarai, U., Bingaman, D. C., Mace, J. L., & Rice, C. V. (2022). Review of possible very high-altitude platforms for stratospheric aerosol injection. *Environmental Research Communications*, 4(3), 031002.

SECURITY ROLE

Two high-profile failures on test deployments of stratospheric aerosol injection (SAI) recently occurred, causing suspicion that they may have been related and not accidental. Because the incidents occurred in different parts of the world and spurred global media coverage, countries leading the efforts are convening to discuss a response.

You play the part of NATO's Airborne Early Warning and Control Force (NAEW&CF). NAEW&CF provides NATO with an airborne surveillance and control capability, crucial for monitoring and coordinating high-altitude operations like SAI. It ensures robust command and control over the airspace, essential for managing the deployment of high-altitude platforms used in SAI. It can detect and respond to potential airborne threats, ensuring security of the delivery platforms.

NAEW&CF operates under NATO's Allied Air Command (AIRCOM). NATO AIRCOM provides command and control of NATO's Integrated Air and Missile Defence mission, which incorporates all measures that contribute to deterring any air and missile threat or to reduce or nullify the effectiveness of hostile air actions.

You should focus your decision making on those options available to military personnel. You are advocating for military positions while identifying where there exist synergies with other roles.

Resources

The resources potentially available to you are those belonging to NATO member countries that would typically be deployed in a non-wartime environment.

Example Actions

These example immediate and long-term actions do not limit your decisions. They are provided solely to start the brainstorming process.

- Continuous review of response measures.
- Changes in levels of readiness or military posture.
- Immediate improvement, implementation, and development of contingency plans.
- Propose a military operation with specific, actionable goals, a timeline, and a list of required resources.
- Recommend and oversee training exercises in preparation for future SAI mishaps.
- Further development of joint military exercises.

Consequences of Inaction

If the incidents during recent test deployments of SAI were not accidental, those responsible may be emboldened to attempt more impactful attacks on SRM plans. Public sentiment against SRM could be strengthened, leading to changes in policy that could make it more difficult to avoid catastrophic levels of global warming.

PUBLIC AFFAIRS ROLE

Two high-profile failures on test deployments of stratospheric aerosol injection (SAI) recently occurred, causing suspicion that they may have been related and not accidental. Because the incidents occurred in different parts of the world and spurred global media coverage, countries leading the efforts are convening to discuss a response.

You play the part of the UN Department of Global Communications. The News and Media Division (NMD) produces news and features about the United Nations and its priorities, including daily print, audio, television, video, photo, digital, and social media content in many languages. With a global audience and wide pick-up by media, non-governmental organizations, private sector and other partners, the NMD generates timely, accurate, impartial and freely available information about United Nations activities around the world. The Outreach Division builds support for the United Nations by fostering dialogue with global constituencies such as civil society, the entertainment industry, media, academia, educators, students, and libraries.

You should focus your decision making on those options available to public relations offices within the UN and member states. You are advocating for public affairs positions while identifying where there exist synergies with other roles.

Resources

As a department within the UN, you have access to a wealth of data about the SRM program, experts on science and science communication, and the ear of news media services around the world. You can also coordinate with other relevant offices at the UN and multi-national organizations like NATO.

Example Actions

These example immediate and long-term actions do not limit your decisions. They are provided solely to start the brainstorming process.

- Analyse shared data to identify threats to future SAI tests.
- Assess the impact of the testing incidents on public opinion around the global.
- Work with governments to promote awareness campaigns of agreed-upon UN policies related to SAI and SRM.
- Develop and rehearse a crisis communication plan to ensure readiness in handling any emergencies or incidents that may arise.

Consequences of Inaction

Failure to engage and communicate effectively with stakeholders can result in a loss of trust and support, making it difficult to gain the necessary approvals and cooperation. Lack of public support and understanding can lead to protests and legal challenges, potentially delaying or halting the operation. Public sentiment against SRM could lead to changes in policy that would make it more difficult to avoid catastrophic levels of global warming.

DIPLOMATIC ROLE

Two high-profile failures on test deployments of stratospheric aerosol injection (SAI) recently occurred, causing suspicion that they may have been related and not accidental. Because the incidents occurred in different parts of the world and spurred global media coverage, countries leading the efforts are convening to discuss a response.

You play the part of the North Atlantic Council. The North Atlantic Council (NAC) is the principal political decision-making body within NATO, consisting of representatives from all member countries. It was established by Article 9 of the North Atlantic Treaty, which formed NATO in 1949. The NAC is responsible for overseeing the implementation of alliance policies and for coordinating defence and security strategies among member states. It meets at least weekly and at various levels, including ambassadors, ministers, and heads of state, to discuss and address issues affecting the alliance. Decisions within the NAC are made by consensus, reflecting the collective will and agreement of all member nations.

You should focus your decision making on those options available only to diplomats and politicians. You are advocating for policy solutions while identifying where there exist synergies with other roles.

Resources

The resources available to you are those belonging to NATO member countries that would typically be deployed in a non-wartime environment. You have the ability to interact and coordinate with any diplomat or agency associated with NATO member states, as well as access to relevant offices and staff at the UN which has coordinated the SRM policy.

Example Actions

These example immediate and long-term actions do not limit your decisions. They are provided solely to start the brainstorming process.

- Assess impacts and assign appropriate consequences to the actions.
- Coordinate action through the UN to assess changes needed to secure future tests.
- Root cause analysis and addressing said cause.
- Propose the creation of a joint task force.

Consequences of Inaction

Failure to secure these operations could undermine trust in international climate intervention efforts, complicating future collaborations. Potential attackers might exploit the situation, leading to increased geopolitical tensions and potential conflicts.

CYBERSECURITY ROLE

Two high-profile failures on test deployments of stratospheric aerosol injection (SAI) recently occurred, causing suspicion that they may have been related and not accidental. Because the incidents occurred in different parts of the world and spurred global media coverage, countries leading the efforts are convening to discuss a response.

You play the part of NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence (CCDCOE) steering committee. CCDCOE provides a hub for cyber defence expertise and cyber operations, offering a range of services including cyber defence exercises, research and development, and coordination of multinational cybersecurity efforts. Their long-term mission is to support member nations with unique interdisciplinary expertise in the field of cyber defence research, training and exercises covering the focus areas of technology, strategy, operations and law. They bring together NATO allies and partners beyond the Alliance, offering an interdisciplinary approach to the most relevant issues in cyber defence through research, trainings and exercises.

You should focus your decision making on those options available to cybersecurity personnel. You are advocating for cyber-intelligence and security positions while identifying where there exist synergies with other roles.

Resources

The resources available to you are those belonging to NATO member countries that would typically be deployed in a non-wartime environment. The UN has been coordinating SRM testing activities, but the NATO CCDCOE has resources which could be used in NATO countries and beyond to assist with diagnosing the past incidents and securing future tests.

Example Actions

These example immediate and long-term actions do not limit your decisions. They are provided solely to start the brainstorming process.

- Investigate insider action possibilities.
- Consider offensive coordination, not capability.
- Threat Information and IT pooling and sharing.
- Ransomware attacks are prevented and impacts lessened.
- Integration of cyber facilities with military capabilities.

Consequences of Inaction

Without proactive cyber diplomacy and defence, critical systems could be further compromised, leading to more extensive damage and long-term security challenges. Manipulation or theft of data related to the SAI deployment could lead to misinformation, impacting the analysis of results and subsequent decision-making processes.

CLIMATE ROLE

Two high-profile failures on test deployments of stratospheric aerosol injection (SAI) recently occurred, causing suspicion that they may have been related and not accidental. Because the incidents occurred in different parts of the world and spurred global media coverage, countries leading the efforts are convening to discuss a response.

You play the part of NATO's Science and Technology Organization (STO). The STO is a NATO subsidiary body having the same legal status than NATO itself and created within the framework of the North Atlantic Treaty signed in 1949. It has been established with a view to meeting to the best advantage the collective needs of NATO, NATO Nations and partner Nations in the fields of Science and Technology. The STO board is chaired by the NATO Chief Scientist, a high-level recognized S&T leader of a NATO nation permanently assigned to the NATO headquarters in Brussels.

You should focus your decision making on those options available to climate and environmental experts. You are advocating for environmental risk-mitigating solutions while providing analysis of the short- and long-term impacts of climate interventions on the ability to meet internationally-agreed upon climate change goals.

Resources

The resources available to you are those belonging to NATO member countries that can be used to support UN efforts on SRM testing. This could include recruiting scientific experts to testify about potential risks, assessing the impacts of alternative policy proposals, and communicating the geospatially varying impacts and uncertainties around SRM deployment.

Example Actions

These example immediate and long-term actions do not limit your decisions. They are provided solely to start the brainstorming process.

- Establish working groups to evaluate the impacts of delays in SRM deployment and alternative options for the use of SAI (e.g., at different latitudes and altitudes).
- Provide experts for interviews as part of communications campaigns after the test incidents.
- Re-evaluate plans for other forms of geoengineering as a contingency if public opinion leads to derailment of SRM policies.

Consequences of Inaction

Inaction in deploying SRM strategies like SAI could lead to worsening climate impacts, with far-reaching consequences for the environment, human health, economies, and global stability. The risks of inaction highlight the urgency of exploring and implementing effective climate mitigation strategies.

Unravelling the Cyber-Physical-Social Infrastructure Climate Change (CPSICC) Nexus

Scenario Background – Solar Radiation Modification¹

This scenario covers the use of stratospheric aerosol interventions (SAI), a form of solar radiation modification (SRM). SAI aims to limit climate change to a non-dangerous level by reducing the Earth's temperature. However, there is low confidence and high levels of uncertainty of the potential impacts of SAI. The objective is to provide sufficient background for participants to understand and engage with the scenario's complexities and potential outcomes projected to 2050.

What is Solar Radiation Modification?

Solar Radiation Modification (SRM), also known as Solar Radiation Management, Radiation Modification Measures or Solar Geoengineering, aims to reflect sunlight back into space to reduce Earth's infrared radiation and the Earth's temperature. SRM does not address the root cause of climate change, which is the increase in greenhouse gases (GHG) in the atmosphere. While there are several different types of SRM, this scenario focuses on stratospheric aerosol interventions (SAI) which pertains to the injection of reflective aerosol particles directly into the stratosphere or a gas which then converts to aerosols that reflect sunlight.

One example would be the intentional release of highly reflective fine particles or their precursors at an altitude of 20–25 km, which could have an effect similar to the Mount Pinatubo eruption on 15 June 1991. The volcano threw about 15 million tons of sulphur dioxide into the stratosphere, where it reacted with water to form a hazy layer of aerosol particles. Strong stratospheric winds spread these aerosol particles around the globe. Over the next 15 months, the average global temperature dropped by about 0.60 °C.

Prompt for participants

- What processes are needed to help nations decide whether novel technology such as SRM technologies should be developed and/or deployed?
- What processes are needed to help nations decide how to assess the risks and benefits of novel technology such as SRM?
- What processes are needed to help nations decide who should be responsible for the development and deployment of novel technology such as SRM?

¹ Information presented herein is heavily based on O'Neill, B., M. van Aalst, Z. Zaiton Ibrahim, L. Berrang Ford, S. Bhadwal, H. Buhaug, D. Diaz, K. Frieler, M. Garschagen, A. Magnan, G. Midgley, A. Mirzabaev, A. Thomas, and R. Warren, 2022: Key Risks Across Sectors and Regions. In: Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lösschke, V. Möller, A. Okem, B. Rama (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, pp. 2411–2538, doi:10.1017/9781009325844.025. Please refer to original for references.

Modelling studies show SAI could reduce surface temperatures and potentially ameliorate some climate change risks, but SAI could also introduce a range of new risks. The effects of SAI would only last if deployment is maintained, with SAI requiring yearly injection of aerosols as the lifetime of aerosols in the stratosphere is 1–3 years. The more intense the SRM deployment, the larger the risk likelihood. Sudden and sustained termination of SRM would result in rapid warming. The magnitude of termination depends on the degree of warming offset.

What are the environmental impacts of Solar Radiation Modification?

Modelling studies have shown SRM has the potential to offset some effects of increasing GHGs on global and regional climate, including the increase in frequency and intensity of extremes of temperature and precipitation, melting of Arctic Sea ice and mountain glaciers, weakening of Atlantic meridional overturning circulation, changes in frequency and intensity of tropical cyclones, and decrease in soil moisture. However, SRM would neither maintain the climate in its present-day state nor return the climate to a pre-industrial state in all regions and in all seasons even when used to fully offset the global mean warming.

Prompt for participants

- How can nations balance the environmental impacts of SRM with the need for sustained water, energy, and food supply?
- What international policies should be implemented to manage the environmental impact SRM?

The regional and seasonal climates of a world with a global mean warming achieved via SRM would be different from a world with similar global mean warming but achieved through mitigation. At the regional scale and seasonal time scale, there could be considerable residual climate change and/or overcompensating change (e.g., more cooling, wetting, or drying than just what is needed to offset warming, drying, or wetting due to anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions), and there is low confidence in the understanding of the climate response to SRM at the regional scale.

SAI may reduce the risk of coral reef bleaching compared with global warming with no SAI but risks to marine life from ocean acidification would remain because SRM does not reduce elevated levels of anthropogenic atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. Reduction in precipitation in Amazonia and central Africa due to SAI is expected to change the biogeography of tropical ecosystems in ways different from both present-day climate and global warming without SAI. This could have large consequences for ecosystem services. SAI may reduce high-fire-risk weather in Australia, Europe, and parts of the Americas, compared with global warming without SAI. Yet SAI could also shift the spatial distribution of acid-induced aluminium soil toxicity into relatively undisturbed ecosystems in Europe and North America. A sudden termination of SAI could bring abrupt changes to the water cycle and place many thousands of species at risk of extinction because the resulting rapid warming would be too fast for species to track the changing climate.

What are the socioeconomic impacts of Solar Radiation Modification?

SRM is likely to have some impacts on crop yields, however, there is currently low confidence and large uncertainty on what the effects could be. For example, in some cases, it may reduce crop productivity at higher latitudes by reducing the growing season length but benefit crop productivity in lower latitudes by reducing heat stress.

Few studies have assessed potential SRM impacts on human health and well-being. However, SRM may shift the zones for communicable diseases, heat stress and extreme weather events, which can trigger new mortality and morbidity patterns. For example, SAI using sulphate aerosols is projected to deplete the ozone layer, increasing mortality from skin cancer. The impact on mortality due to air pollution is uncertain and would depend on aerosol type and deployment. This is because, SAI could increase mortality due to an increase in particulate matter due to offsetting warming, reduced precipitation, and deposition of SAI

aerosols, but SAI could also reduce mortality due to surface-level ozone exposure.

Manipulating climate via SRM can lead to extreme weather events including flood, drought, and windstorms, these triggering property losses, and other claims. A sudden implementation of SAI could force the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) system, which may, in turn, increase the risk of diseases such as severe cholera in certain parts of the world. Studies considering only mean annual temperature and precipitation predict that SAI stabilises global temperature at its present-day level which could help to reduce income inequality between countries compared with the highest warming pathway (RCP8.5).

Some integrated assessment model scenarios have included SAI suggesting that the indirect costs and benefits to welfare dominate since the direct economic cost of SAI itself is expected to be relatively low.

Prompt for participants

- How can nations balance the socioeconomic impacts of SRM with the need for sustained water, energy, and food supply?
- What processes are needed to decide whether and how industries and/or communities would be compensated if negatively impacted by SRM technology?
- What processes are needed to decide how transboundary impacts will be dealt with?

What are the geopolitical considerations of Solar Radiation Modification?

SRM deployment could carry significant geopolitical risks by introducing novel risks for international collaboration and peace. For example, conflicting temperature preferences between countries may lead to counter-geoengineering measures such as the deliberate release of warming agents or the destruction of deployment equipment. Game-theoretic models and laboratory experiments indicate that a powerful actor or group with a higher preference for SRM may use SAI to cool the planet beyond what is socially optimal, imposing welfare losses on others, although this cooling does not necessarily imply that excluded countries would be worse off relative to a world of unmitigated warming. In this context, counter-geoengineering may promote international cooperation or lead to large welfare losses. In addition, potential international power rivalry could arise with the involvement of the military in geoengineering projects². Countries might be inclined to monitor geoengineering aircraft, particularly if they were to encroach on their airspace.

It is possible that cyberattacks could be used to eliminate rivals' geoengineering capacity. For example, opposing states might seek to neutralise geoengineering potential by destroying airbases and planes with cyberattacks. This could lead to military escalation and conflict.

There is concern that deploying SAI could potentially obstruct ongoing and future mitigation efforts. This is because it could give decision-makers the impression that they no longer need to mitigate emissions, accelerating emissions further. There are calls for SRM not to be the main policy response to climate change but instead be viewed as a possible supplement to achieving sustained net negative CO₂ emission levels globally.

There is recognition that SRM research has been conducted predominantly by a relatively small number of experts in the Global North, and greater participation from diverse peoples and geographies is needed in setting research agendas and

Prompt for participants

- What processes are needed to ensure disruptive technologies such as SRM are developed and adopted responsibly?
- What can nations do to protect disruptive technologies such as SRM from interference and manipulation by potential adversaries?

² Adam Lockyer & Jonathan Symons (2019) The national security implications of solar geoengineering: in Australian perspective, *Australian Journal of International Affairs*, 73:5, 485-503, DOI: 10.1080/10357718.2019.1662768

research governance priorities and undertaking research. Unequal power relations in participation could influence SRM research governance and potential policy implications. It is also possible that research and outdoor experimentation could have negative outcomes and impact eventual deployment. Effective regulation is needed to avoid undesirable outcomes.

What are strategic considerations of Solar Radiation Modification?

The benefits and risks of SRM need to be evaluated in context with the risks of climate change and will depend on several factors. The release of compounds into the atmosphere impacts many countries. The nation which deploys SRM may not be the one that suffers harmful side effects. Deciding which legal frameworks and governance for negative side effects to apply will be important. For example, models are needed to define what cooling agent is used and how much, as well as for how long and where it should be injected into the stratosphere.

Due to current low levels of confidence and uncertainty of the potential risks resulting from SRM, investment in research studies, including improved modelling is critical for adequate decision-making. For example, as models are currently under development, it is difficult to say which countries/regions would benefit or be harmed by consequent changes in climate and weather patterns. When designing and evaluating SAI scenarios, biome-specific responses need to be considered in risk evaluation. For SAI, large-scale outdoor experiments could be transboundary.

Governance arrangements are co-evolving but currently, there is no dedicated, formal international SRM governance for research, development, demonstration, or deployment. Some multilateral agreements—such as the UN Convention on Biological Diversity or the Vienna Convention on the Protection of the Ozone Layer—indirectly and partially cover SRM, but none is comprehensive. While current governance objectives range broadly, from prohibition to enabling research and potential deployment, there is agreement that SRM governance should cover all interacting stages of research through to any potential, eventual deployment with rules, institutions, and norms. There are calls for governance and SRM to also include broader public participation and political legitimacy, guarding against potential risks and harms relevant across a full range of scenarios, and ensuring that SRM is considered only as a part of a broader portfolio of responses to climate change.

Conclusion

SRM is a novel technology, and more studies are needed to better understand the potential for SRM to reduce climate risk and/or the potential risks that deploying SRM could bring to people and ecosystems. International cooperation is critical to developing a common understanding of research needs and results, promoting knowledge gains and resource savings, as well as improving transparency and ensuring responsible experimentation and/or deployment of SRM internationally.

Further information available at:

- <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/chapter/chapter-16/>
- <https://www.whitehouse.gov/ostp/news-updates/2023/06/30/congressionally-mandated-report-on-solar-radiation-modification/>
- <https://www.swissre.com/institute/research/sonar/sonar2023/solar-radiation-risks-climate-change.html>
- <https://www.epfl.ch/research/domains/irgc/spotlight-on-risk-series/a-risk-risk-assessment-framework-for-solar-radiation-modification/>

Prompt for participants

- What processes are needed to ensure transparency when disseminating research findings from the evaluation of SRM technology?
- What international governance arrangements are needed to regulate research, development, and deployment of SRM technology?

SRM 2050

Climate

- SRM avoided many of the consequences of climate change, and the economy is strong. There are some environmental impacts, (e.g., acid rain) but nothing major. Emissions have increased at an accelerating rate since the 2030s when the effectiveness of SRM was demonstrated and adopted.

Geopolitics/Governance

- After 2030, the UNSC centralized control over SRM. A successful UN regulatory framework was created to govern SAI deployment, compensation for negatively affected states, contributions to costs, etc

SRM

- SRM is delivered by a global fleet of drones using space-based, automated sensors. SRM enables less restrictive economic activity and is popular.

Social

- SRM benefits are widespread, any geographic-specific issues are resolved by 2050. Economic strength resulting from SRM allows for more expensive solutions to fix externalities.

Attack

- A nation-state actor threatens to conduct a cyber attack that suspends SRM operations as ransom.

Signals

- Earth will rapidly warm and quickly accumulate climate change impacts from GHG accumulated since 2030 (e.g., droughts, floods, extreme heat).